

ELECTRONIC AND DISTANCE LEARNING FOR MEDICAL PERSONNEL.

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ABSTRACT

To access high-performance reviews of each medical indicator, the staff working with it depends on online, up-to-date information technology and innovation. Today, high-performance medical indicators require a high level of automation.

INTRODUCTION. To improve their knowledge, enable employees to make rational decisions, and successfully perform their other duties, medical staff are required to have not only detailed and reliable information, but also the ability to quickly work with this information, analyze, summarize, and prepare relevant documents on this basis. Studies show that management service specialists spend 30 to 80 percent of their working time working with this information. This is natural, because working with information is a crucial factor in effective management.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Telemedicine is a telecommunications and information technology used to treat patients remotely. Thanks to it, no distance can be a barrier to treatment for the patient, and patients can use medical services. This is especially convenient for patients living in hard-to-reach areas. In addition, in emergency situations, it allows you to save the lives of patients in critical condition remotely.

Benefits of Telemedicine

1. Accessibility

Telemedicine removes geographical barriers, enabling patients in rural and remote areas to access specialists. For example, teledermatology allows patients to share high-quality images with specialists for faster diagnoses.

2. Cost Efficiency

For patients: Eliminates travel expenses and lost work hours.

For providers: Reduces infrastructure costs (e.g., fewer physical consultations mean lower overhead costs).

3. Patient Engagement

Remote care platforms encourage active participation by offering personalized health tracking and reminders. Chronic disease management apps, for instance, provide patients with insights into their health metrics.

4. Crisis Response

During the pandemic, telemedicine ensured continuity of care while minimizing infection risks. It also plays a role in disaster zones where traditional healthcare services are inaccessible.

Figure 1. Video conferencing tools in medicine.

Today, the areas of application of telemedicine technologies are: Remote interactive training;

In the study of new technologies and equipment;

Remote videoconferencing for seriously ill patients using high technology;

Mobile and mobile telemedicine complex emergency assistance telemaslaxat berish;

Video aloqa uskunalari:

Video calling applications such as WebEx and Skype are a great way for people in hard-to-reach areas to stay in touch with healthcare workers. Instead of waiting for medical personnel to arrive in remote rural areas, this method of medical care can be used immediately, and is being used in many countries, such as Brazil..

Diagnostic visualization mobile centers:

In rural areas, where it is difficult to fully equip diagnostic centers with X-ray equipment and analysis, mobile diagnostic imaging centers and laboratory-type points are of great importance in sending the received information to larger centers and making a real diagnosis. In general, doctors have this opportunity and can actually treat the patient. Specialists of the California non-profit medical organization Kaiser Permanente are receiving and treating more than 800 patients per month, 50 percent more patients for the population in hard-to-reach areas than they would normally receive.

Remote inspection

Despite the advantages of video communication equipment, the opportunities offered by new technologies in emergency situations, for the elderly or in the event of an attack of chronic diseases and other medical conditions, cannot replace a doctor in providing prompt first aid. For this purpose, new modern devices have been developed, thanks to which patients can regularly monitor their health at home, regardless of where they are. The devices transmit the received data to the current control centers, where the patient's health status is under the control of doctors. The doctor, no matter how far away he is geographically, will be able to immediately take the necessary measures and give life-saving instructions. This is the best opportunity to support the health of patients.

Medical devices for the development of local social structures: Patients who can help other patients is a great way to expand the scope of medical care. In some cases, patients do not need professional medical care, but simply need advice from other patients who have encountered a similar problem. Online methods of electronic communities, such as PatientsLikeMe.com, allow groups of patients to communicate, regardless of geographical location, without increasing costs, and patients only need to have a mobile phone or computer to use the service. Africa is particularly prominent among those who are using telemedicine devices effectively on a large scale. Virtual Doctors is a non-profit "simple telemedicine software designed specifically for rural Africa, facilitating communication between a team of remote medical professionals, known as medical guides, and medical experts, enabling diagnosis and treatment."

Telemedicine is becoming increasingly popular, although it cannot replace doctors, especially in rural areas, but it is already finding its place in providing immediate access to medical services and routine health care. It also provides immediate access to medical services in remote areas that are difficult to reach. The goal of advanced technologies is always to build bridges towards convenience, and telemedicine is a great example of this.

Figure 2. Intercity and interdistrict video conference

DISCUSSION

Mobile Telemedicine Laboratory-Scaesnet. Mobile Telemedicine Laboratory is a high-level system that is used to combat HIV, malaria and other infectious diseases. MTL is important for screening the general population and providing first aid. Epidemic situation monitoring and control system using information and communication technologies.

CONCLUSION

In this article, the main goal of electronic and distance learning, information support for medical workers is to work with existing data, analyze and generalize them, which serve as a source for making rational decisions. The large volume of information flows, the often repetitive operations of collecting, storing, working with and using various data clearly demonstrate the importance of using the most modern information technologies in the service of personnel management.

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